

DIFFERENTIATION OF EDUCATION THROUGH MODERN APPROACHES

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In the modern educational process, taking into account the individual characteristics, learning pace, interests and intellectual needs of students has become one of the most important tasks of the teacher. Traditional teaching methods implied an approach to all students with the same requirements. However, in the current era of globalization, each student thinks differently, the speed of mastering the material also differs, and personal abilities are manifested to varying degrees. Therefore, the differentiation of education — that is, teaching students based on their capabilities, abilities and needs — has become an urgent issue.

The main goal of differentiated education is to create a learning process for each student that is appropriate to his or her personal level of development, to develop the student's strengths, and to provide individual assistance in areas of difficulty. Today, modern approaches, innovative pedagogical technologies, digital tools and concepts of competency-based education play an important role in the effective organization of this process.

Differentiated education is the organization of the learning process for a group of students, based on their interests, level of knowledge, level of preparation and psychological characteristics, using different methods, different learning tasks or exercises of varying complexity. This method develops the student as a person, and allows the teacher to study each student in depth.[1]

The main principles of differentiation are:

individual approach;

teaching according to the student's interests and needs;

giving different levels of tasks;

presenting educational material from simple to complex;

flexibility in the teaching process.[2]

While in traditional teaching all students are given the same task, in differentiated education each student works at the level of his or her own capabilities, but the ultimate goal is common.

Today's education system is saturated with modern pedagogical methods. All of them, while increasing the effectiveness of education, also facilitate differentiation.

Competency-based education assumes that students acquire not only knowledge, but also practical skills and qualifications. Tasks are offered for different competencies so that each student can develop according to his or her abilities.

For example, if a student is inclined to logical thinking, he or she will study mathematical tasks in depth; and creative students are offered design, graphic, and project work. In this way, each student succeeds in their own field.

STEAM (Science, Technology, Engineering, Art, Mathematics) is an integrative approach to science that allows students to combine different areas.

This approach enhances differentiated learning because:

creative students participate in projects through art and design,

technical students build structures,

analytical students solve problems mathematically.

This creates opportunities for each student.[3]

Project-based learning (PBL) enhances students' independent research. In the process of differentiation, projects are selected based on the student's abilities and interests.

For example:

technological project,

social project,

creative project,

research project.[4]

This approach takes into account the differences between students and adapts the learning pace to each.

Today, the digital education system allows students to independently select and complete exercises appropriate to their level.

For example:

online platforms,

interactive tests,

animated videos,

artificial intelligence-based programs.[6]

Digital education automatically determines the level of the student and offers educational material that is appropriate for his strengths and weaknesses.

Modular education divides the educational material into sections that can be mastered independently. Each module contains:

objectives,

practical tasks,

control questions. The student masters the modules at a pace convenient for him.

This approach directs students to self-education and ensures individual development.

Differentiation of education makes it possible to achieve the following results:

Since the material corresponds to the student's personal interests, the internal need for learning increases.

A fast learner is engaged in additional tasks, while a slow learner is not so quick to get acquainted with complex material.

Each student grows independently according to his or her abilities. This also facilitates the process of choosing a future profession.

The teacher provides individual assistance to each student with his or her difficulties.

Each student receives not the same knowledge, but knowledge appropriate to his or her capabilities. This forms a fair education system.

Differentiated learning in a school setting can be organized through the following methods:

A, B, C level tasks (from simple to complex);

Role-based group work;

Logical cards;

Tests according to the level of mastery;

Customized homework;

Working with texts of varying complexity;

Individual learning plans.[5]

These methods protect students from excessive stress and increase their self-confidence.

In conclusion, Modern approaches increase the effectiveness of differentiated learning, create the opportunity to teach according to the individual abilities and needs of each student. STEAM, project-based learning, modular approach, digital technologies and competency-based learning have become the foundations of differentiated learning.

In today's globalization environment, the development of the individual potential of the student, his upbringing as an independent thinker and creative person is the main task of modern education. Therefore, differentiated education is one of the most important factors in shaping the future generation as a competitive and creative person.

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